

A STUDY ON THE MATERIAL AND GEOMETRICALLY NONLINEAR BEHAVIOR
OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Won-Man Cho, Principal Researcher,
ADD. P.O. Box 35, Yu-song, Dae-Jeon, 305-600

Young-Shin Lee, Professor,
Department of Mechanical Design Engineering, Chung-Nam National University, Yu-Song, Dae-Jeon, 305-704
and

Sung-Kie Youn, Associate Professor,
Department of Mechanical Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology,
Yu-song, Dae-Jeon, 305-701, Korea

ABSTRACT

In this study, the nonlinear behavior of laminated composite structures was analyzed by a nonlinear finite element formulation using the degenerated shell element. The finite element program developed included the geometric, material and combined nonlinearities. The geometrically nonlinear problems were analyzed through the finite element formulation by the total Lagrangian method. Problems associated with the material nonlinearity were analyzed by applying the material degradation model in which failure progressed in the matrix and in the matrix-fiber interface after initial failure occurred.

Present analysis results on several anisotropic plate and shell structures were in good agreement with other exact and existing numerical solutions. Two kinds of experimental studies were performed to verify the analysis and to observe the nonlinear behavior of composite structures. In one experiment, four-sided clamped laminated composite square plates subject to the concentrated load at the central point were employed. In the other experiment, filament wound(f/w) antisymmetric tubes subject to internal pressure were conducted. The results of combined nonlinear analysis agreed well with the experimental data.

Keywords: composite laminated plate, composite laminated shell, finite element method, geometric nonlinearity, material nonlinearity, combined nonlinearity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composite materials had been used mostly for secondary structural members before 1980. Recently, their effective usage as primary structural members in the wing and body of aircraft, rocket motor case of spacecraft and pressure vessels is being increased due to many advantages such as high strength to weight and high modulus to weight ratios [1]. The primary composite structures are employed in the form of thin laminated plate and shell because of light weight requirement, so that geometric and material nonlinear analyses are required to predict the nonlinear behavior.

In this regard, studies on the nonlinear behavior of composite structures are limited except some geometric nonlinear analyses[2,3] and a few elastic-plastic approaches using Huber-Mises yield criterion[4]. Thus, efforts are continued to consider the material or the combined (both geometric and material) nonlinearity using the finite element method.

The objective of this study is to develop a nonlinear finite element program for analyzing the material and combined nonlinearities caused by material degradation in the matrix after initial failure. In order to verify the finite element formulation for those nonlinearities, experimental studies for two types of composite structures were conducted: (1) four-sided clamped carbon/epoxy laminated composite square plates subject to concentrated load at the center, and (2) filament wound antisymmetric tubes subject to internal pressure.

2. NONLINEAR MODEL AND THEORY

2.1 Constitutive Equation

The stress-strain relation for the kth layer of laminated structure in the material direction (1, 2, 3 directions) can be expressed as

$$\{\epsilon\}_k = [S]_k \{\sigma\}_k \quad (1)$$

where $[S]_k$ is the reduced stiffness matrix of the kth layer.

Neglecting the strain energy corresponding to stress perpendicular to the mid-plane of each layer and assuming a plane stress state with $\sigma_3=0$, one obtains

$$\{\sigma\}_k = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_{12}, \sigma_{13}, \sigma_{23}\} \quad (2)$$

If material axes, 1 and 2, are rotated by a certain angle θ with respect to local axes, x' and y' , stress and strain components follow as

$$\{\sigma\}_k = [T] \{\sigma'\}_k \quad (3)$$

$$\{\epsilon\}_k = [T'] \{\epsilon'\}_k \quad (4)$$

$$\{\sigma'\}_k = [T]^{-1} [C]_k [T'] \{\epsilon'\}_k = [D]_k \{\epsilon'\}_k \quad (5)$$

where $[T]$ and $[T']$ are transformed matrices, $[D]_k$ is the transformed reduced stiffness matrix of the kth layer and $\{\sigma'\}$ and $\{\epsilon'\}$ are stress and strain vectors in local coordinates.

2.2 Transverse Shear Deformation

For isotropic materials having the transverse shear modulus to the in-plane modulus ratio of 1/2.6, the effect of shear deformation needs to be considered when thickness/width $\geq 1/10$. In this case, shear deformation has a large effect on strain, stress and buckling load. In the case of composite materials having the transverse shear modulus to the in-plane modulus ratio of 1/6-1/80, the shear deformation effect has to be considered even when thickness/width $\geq 1/30$. The transverse shear deformation plays an important role for predicting the delamination failure in multilayered composite structures.

Various deformation theories have been proposed to analyze composite plate and shell. The present study implemented the first shear deformation theory that satisfies the continuity condition of shear deformation between layers. The shear strain distribution is generally assumed to be a quadratic function of thickness. In this regard, shear correction factor was introduced in order to approximate, on an average basis, the transverse shear strain energy[4]. The shear correction factor k was applied to the shear modulus. Consequently, the shear correction factor κ_1 in the xz plane can be obtained as

$$\kappa_1 = \bar{U}_s / U_s = K_x^2 \left[h \cdot \bar{G}_{13} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} S^2(z) / G_{13}(z) dz \right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

where K_x is the flexural stiffness in the x direction, G_{13} is the average shear modulus in the xz plane, and $S(z)$ is the shear stress shape function.

The shear correction factor κ_2 in the yz plane can be calculated in the same way, and the value of κ for a homogeneous cross section is 5/6.

2.3 Material Nonlinearity Model by Material Degradation

When initial failure occurs, the commonly applied classical laminate theory assumes that the matrix of damaged layer loses the stiffness and additional loads are sustained by fibers only. The analyses based on this assumption showed a large difference when compared with the actual behavior. Moreover, the material property degradation due to the matrix damage propagation is microscopically difficult to obtain. In this study, the matrix degradation factor (DF) obtained from macroscopic

experiments [5] was implemented to each step of the nonlinear iterative calculation. It was assumed that the material nonlinear behavior occurs by the local failure propagation. Consequently, as load increases, the laminate will be damaged more until it reaches the saturation level before the ultimate failure.

Three dimensional Tsai-Wu failure criterion was used for initial failure equation under the multi-axis stress state, i.e.,

$$f(\sigma) = F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j + F_i \sigma_i \leq 1 \quad i, j=1, 2, \dots, 6 \quad (7)$$

where F_i and F_{ij} are the second and fourth rank tensors, respectively. Equation 7 can be rewritten as

$$F_1 \sigma_1^2 + F_2 \sigma_2^2 + F_{11}^2 \sigma_1^2 + F_{22}^2 \sigma_2^2 + F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + F_{44} \sigma_{23}^2 + F_{55} \sigma_{13}^2 + F_{66} \sigma_{12}^2 \leq 1 \quad (8)$$

The stiffness degradations due to the matrix property reduction are given by

$$E_2 = (DF1) \cdot E_2^0 \quad G_{12} = (DF2) \cdot G_{12}^0 \quad \nu_{12} = (DF3) \cdot \nu_{12}^0 \quad (9)$$

where the superscript zero denotes intact moduli values.

The incremental/iterative scheme was used for nonlinear analysis, and Newton-Raphson iterative method was used to calculate the progressive degradation of material properties.

3. FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

To avoid the complexities of general shell theories and to discretize directly the three-dimensional equations, the isoparametric degenerated shell element with independent rotational and displacement degrees of freedom are employed in which the three-dimensional stresses and strains are degenerated to shell behavior[6].

3.1 Coordinates and Displacement Fields

The external face of the shell element is curved and the curvilinear coordinates of a point within the element can be obtained from the nodal coordinates of the mid-plane with the cartesian coordinates.

Two curvilinear coordinates ξ, η in the mid-plane of the shell and a linear coordinate ζ in the thickness direction vary between -1 and 1 on the respective face of the element. Thus, a relationship between the cartesian coordinates and the curvilinear coordinates for any point in the shell element can be written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i(\xi, \eta) \begin{Bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{Bmatrix}_{mid} + \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \frac{\zeta}{2} \underline{V}_{3i} \quad (10)$$

where $N_i(\xi, \eta)$ is a element shape function of isoparametric element, n is the number of nodes per element, and \underline{V}_{3i} defines a vector whose length is the shell thickness.

If strains in the direction normal to the mid-plane are assumed to be negligible, one can obtain the global displacements

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ w_i \end{Bmatrix}_{mid} + \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \frac{\zeta}{2} [V_{1i}, -V_{2i}] \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_i \\ \beta_i \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where $\underline{V}_{2i}, \underline{V}_{1i}$ are mutually orthogonal unit vectors, and α_i, β_i are corresponding rotations.

In Equation 11, N_i satisfies the compatibility conditions, and hence the displacement compatibility is maintained between adjacent elements.

3.2 Geometric Nonlinear Equations

To analyze geometric nonlinear problems, total Lagrangian formulation was employed and large deflections and moderate rotations in the sense of Von-Karman hypotheses were introduced.

The same incremental and iterative procedures as for the material nonlinear analysis were adopted. In this process, the equilibrium equation will not be exactly satisfied and a system of residual forces will exist so that

$$\{\phi(a)\}_k^n = \int_V [\bar{B}]^T \{\sigma\}_k^n - \{f\}^n \approx 0 \quad (12)$$

where $[B]$ is the strain-displacement matrix, $\{\sigma\}$ is the current stress vector, $\{f\}$ is the externally applied force vector, superscript n signifies the load increment number, and the subscript k is the iteration cycle number within each increment.

Taking the variation of Equation 12 with respect to a displacement variation da , the tangential stiffness matrix can be written as

$$\{d\phi\} = \int_V [d\bar{B}]^T \{\sigma\} dV + \int_V [\bar{B}]^T \{d\sigma\} dV = [K_T] da \quad (13)$$

The strain-displacement matrix $[B]$ can be separated into the linear part $[B_L]$ and the nonlinear part $[B_{NL}]$,

$$[\bar{B}] = [B_L] + [B_{NL}] \quad (14)$$

$$[d\bar{B}]^T = [dB_{NL}]^T \quad (15)$$

From Equations 14 and 15, Equation 13 can be rewritten as

$$\{d\phi\} = \int_V [dB_{NL}]^T \{\sigma\} dV + [\bar{K}] da \quad (16)$$

where

$$[\bar{K}] = \int_V [B]^T [D] [B] dV = [K_L] + [K_{NL}] \quad , \quad \int_V [dB_{NL}]^T \sigma dV = [K_\sigma] da \quad (17)$$

Then, one can obtain

$$\{d\phi\} = ([K_\sigma] + [K_L] + [K_{NL}]) da = [K_T] da \quad (18)$$

where $[K_L]$ is the infinitesimal displacement stiffness matrix, $[K_{NL}]$ is the large displacement stiffness matrix, and $[K_\sigma]$ is the initial stress matrix.

4. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

To assess the validity and exactness of the finite element formulation and to establish its range of applicability, a number of problems were investigated as described below. In the present study, the 8-node Serendipity element was employed. To avoid the solution locking occurred as the thickness of structure reduces, the present analysis utilized the reduced integration rule (2x2 Gauss integration) and a great improvement could be achieved.

4.1 Laminated Anisotropic Plate under Uniform Transverse Loading

The linear and large deflection analyses of a 16 layer laminated square plate with all edges clamped subjected to a uniformly distributed transverse loading were conducted. The lay-up of this plate is composed of $[45/0_2/\pm 45/90_2]_s$, and material properties used were $E_1=131$ GPa, $E_2=6.41$ GPa, and $\nu_{12}=0.38$. Uniform load of 125 Kpa was applied into 32 load steps. The load-deflection behavior is shown in Figure 3. Compared to the alternative solution by Saigal[2], the present analysis showed a good agreement.

4.2 Glass/Epoxy Thin-Walled Cylinder under Internal Pressure

The linear and large deflection analyses of a thin-walled cylinder clamped at both ends subjected to internal pressure were performed. The material properties were assumed to be orthotropic and the elastic constants used were $E_1=517.13$ GPa, $E_2=13.79$ GPa and $\nu_{12}=0.25$.

The load-deflection results are plotted in Figure 4, where they are compared with the numerical results by Saigal[2]. In this case, a good agreement can also be seen.

However, the analysis results on the present material system for combined nonlinearity was compared with the experimental values only because there are no existing analysis results available.

5. EXPERIMENTS

5.1 Specimen Preparation

To fabricate the laminated plate specimen, the unidirectional prepreg tape was cut to a desired angle, then stacked and cured according to the predetermined cure cycle in an autoclave. The material properties and the size of the specimen are presented in Table 2 and 3, respectively.

Tubular specimens were made by wet helical filament winding process. They were hardened by predetermined curing cycle in an oven rotating at a constant speed. The shape and dimension of the tubular specimens are shown in Figure 5. Material properties, winding angle and manufacturing condition of the tubular specimens are shown in Table 2 and 4.

5.2 Experimental Procedure

The plate specimen was loaded by a Instron testing machine with 5 ton loadcell and the displacement was measured by a dial gage at the central bottom of the specimen.

The tubular specimen was subjected to internal pressure by an air-compressed hydropump attached with accumulator.

A strain gage capable of measuring large strain to 20 percents was attached at the central part of the tube. The pressure-strain curve was plotted in the axial and circumferential directions.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the case of the 8 layer carbon T300/epoxy plate specimen with 1.0mm thickness, the combined nonlinear analyses agreed well with the experimental results as shown in Figure 6.

In the case of the carbon T300/epoxy and E-glass/epoxy plate specimens with 3.0mm thickness, the experimental results tended to agree with the material nonlinear analyses rather than the combined nonlinear analyses as shown in Figure 7 and 8. One possible explanation for this is that large increase of displacement occurred due to the rapid progress of penetration at the local load contact point.

For the $[\pm 45^\circ]$ tubular specimen of 0.9 mm thickness, the internal pressure-radial displacement behavior is seen in Figure 9(a), and they generally show a good agreement with the combined nonlinear analyses.

In Figure 9(b), the comparison shows some difference in strain between the two results. The cause of this discrepancy can be attributed to the nonuniform thickness distribution, machining process, residual stress during curing process and material inhomogeneity.

For the $[\pm 55^\circ]$ tubular specimen of 0.9mm thickness, the internal pressure-radial displacement and the internal pressure-strain behavior are seen in Figure 10(a) and (b) respectively, and they show a good agreement with the combined nonlinear analysis results.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The nonlinear finite element formulation using the degenerated shell element was made for the analysis of various laminated composite structures. The nonlinear program developed included the geometric and material nonlinearities, and the combination of the two.

The geometric and nonlinear problems were analyzed, and the results proved to agree well with other exact and existing numerical solutions.

For the analysis of material nonlinear problems, material nonlinear and combined nonlinear analyses were performed. A number of experiments were also conducted for laminated plates and

filament wound tubes. It has been observed that the combined nonlinear analysis results showed a good agreement with the experimental values.

Based on this observation, the finite element program developed here can be used to predict the geometric, material and combined nonlinear behavior of composite structures.

REFERENCES

1. Chamis, C.C., Mechanics of Composite Materials: Past, Present and Future, Journal of Composites Technology & Research, Vol.11, No.1, pp.3-14, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1989.
2. Saigal, S., Kapania, R., Yang, T.Y., Geometrically Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis of Imperfect Laminated Shells, J. of Comp. Mat., Vol.20, pp.197-214, Technomic Publishing Co. Inc, 1986.
3. Chang, T.Y., Sawamiphakdi, K., Large Deformation Analysis of Laminated Shells by Finite Element Method, Computers & Structures, Vol.13, pp.331-335, Pergamon Press Ltd., 1981.
4. Owen, D.R.J., Figueriras, J.A., Anisotropic Elasto-Plastic Finite Element Analysis of Thick and Thin Plates and Shells, Int.J.Num.Meth.Engng, Vol.19, pp.541-566, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., 1983.
5. Tsai, S.W., Composites Design, 4th Edition, Think Composites: Dayton, 1988, pp.11-1~12-25.
6. Zienkiewicz, O.C., The Finite Element Method, 3rd ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1977, pp.398-422.

Table 1. Degradation factor(DF) values based on matrix degradation

Properties	Material	Carbon T300/epoxy	E-glass/epoxy
DF (E_m^*)		0.20	0.10
DF1 (E_2^*)		0.31	0.14
DF2 (G_{12}^*)		0.27	0.11
DF3 (ν_{12}^*)		0.20	0.10

* means degradation from intact to degraded matrix.

Table 2. Composite properties of laminated plate and f/w tube specimens

Properties	Material	Carbon T300/epoxy (for plate specimen)	E-glass/epoxy (for plate specimen)	Carbon T300/6005 epoxy (for f/w tube specimen)
E_1 (GPa)		135.4	38.6	132.11
E_2 (GPa)		9.6	8.27	8.18
G_{12} (GPa)		4.8	4.14	5.00
ν_{12}		0.31	0.26	0.33
F_{LT} (MPa)		1933.0	1062.0	1416.00
F_{LC} (MPa)		1932.3	608.1	1020.00
F_{TT} (MPa)		51.0	31.0	33.65
F_{TC} (MPa)		51.0	118.0	141.20
F_S (MPa)		84.0	72.0	70.00

Table 3. Dimension and laminated angle of laminated plate specimens

Material	Laminated angle	Dimension (mm)	Thickness (mm)
Carbon/epoxy	[0/15/-15/90] _s	150x150	1.0
Carbon/epoxy	[0 ₃ /15 ₃ /-15 ₃ /90 ₃] _s	150x150	3.0
E-glass/epoxy	[0/15/-15/90] _s	150x150	3.0

Table 4. Winding angle and other conditions of f/w tube specimens

Material	Pattern	$\pm 45^\circ$	$\pm 55^\circ$
Carbon T300/6005 epoxy	Band width(mm)	7.5	7.5
	Counter	53.0	37.0
	End	3.0	3.0
	Tension(kg/end)	1.2	1.2
	Thickness	0.9	0.9
	Layer	1.0	1.0

Figure 1. Material and local axes in the laminated structure

Figure 2. Global and nodal coordinate system

Figure 3. Large deflection behavior curve of the 16-layer graphite/epoxy plate under uniform lateral load

Figure 4. Large deflection behavior curve of the thin walled cylinder

Figure 5. Configuration of f/w tube specimen

Figure 6. Comparison between present FEM analysis and experiment in the plate specimen

Figure 7. Comparison between present FEM analysis and experiment in the plate specimen

Figure 8. Comparison between present FEM analysis and experiment in the plate specimen

Figure 9. Comparison between present FEM analysis and experiment in the f/w tube specimen

Figure 10. Comparison between present FEM analysis and experiment in the f/w tube specimen